

Screening for resistance to leaf spot

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Nine of 74 selected lines planted in a nursery at Rembang, Central Java, were resistant to brown spot *Helminthosporium oryzae* and stackburn *Alternaria padwickii*. These were Siam 1019, IR2071-105-4, IR2071-588-6, IR2031-254-2-3, IR2055-219-1-3, RP 633-680-1-1-1-1, ARC 5793, Balop Merah 910, and Madura Samba.

Lines resistant to narrow brown leaf spot, *Cercospora oryzae*

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Thirty-two lines from the local collection and 23 lines from the Observational

Yield Trial and from local collection found to be resistant to narrow brown leaf spot. Sukamandi, Indonesia

Observational Yield Trial	Local collection
IR796 C-MR-143-24	S. Hitam Segon
IR1514 A-5597-2	Tarak Karo
IR1909-1-3-3	Puy
IR2031-354-2-3	Tambu
IR2031-422-3-3	Paya Bokot
IR2070-78-2-3	Munte
IR2070-178-2-3	Puket Garu
IR2070-381-1-5-8	Kasih Beranak
IR2070-652-5-4-11	Gadis Kebalsi
IR2070-939-3-4-10	Rendah Renumi
IR2071-105-9-4	Umbang Katib
IR2071-573-3-3-14	Rampone
IR2071-588-3-5	S. Buyung
IR2078-71-2	Saeful Putih
IR2688-43-4-3	Lakaton Abang
IR2798-88-3	Gadabung Gundill
Si 01 b-218-3	Siem Ganol
B 1990	Laketu Mangan
b-MR-43467-3B	Pakui
B 1990	Sipanci
b-MR-43534-2B	R. Jawa
B 1990	Disi
b-MR-43534-2B	Raden Rata
B 2360-6-4-5	Bakaton Panas
B 2360-8-4-5	Lakaton Karamunting
B 2932-2-1-4-1-3	Isip
	Karang Dukuh
	Minai

Yield Trial were selected at Sukamandi, West Java, for resistance to narrow brown leaf spot *Cercospora oryzae* (see table). The new IRRI releases — PB26, PB28, PB30, PB32, and PB34 — were all rated highly susceptible to narrow brown leaf spot.

Reaction of some gall midge crosses to false smut at Mandya, Karnataka, India

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In kharif 1975, a heavy incidence of false smut *Ustilagoidea virens* was recorded on the F₃ progeny of some crosses made for gall midge at the V.C. Farm, Mandya. The disease symptoms were characterized by transformation of the paddy grains to greenish-black spore balls (smut balls) of velvety appearance. The glumes of the spikelets can still be seen on the spore masses. The disease incidence was severe enough to distinguish susceptible crosses and

susceptible F₃ lines within crosses. The plants within each progeny showing false smut were counted and recorded for all crosses. Analyses of these data are based on the rating scale system suggested in the "Standard Evaluation Systems for Rice" published by IRRI, 1975.

C2 had an incidence of less than 5 percent and was hence, moderately resistant to false smut (Table 1). C1 and C3 had less than 25 percent incidence. C4 recorded an incidence of 41.8 percent, and shall be considered susceptible.

The number of F₃ progeny in each cross has been grouped according to the percent incidence of false smut (Table 2).

No F₃ line showed a resistant reaction to false smut. However, some progeny with moderate levels of resistance (1–5% incidence) were recovered in C1 and C2. Most of the F₃ progeny exhibited from 6 to 25 percent disease incidence. In the cross C4, 2 out of 15 F₃ lines studied recorded disease incidence that exceeded 50 percent, and hence were classified as very susceptible.

Table 1. Incidence of false smut disease (*U. virens*) in progeny of crosses made for gall midge resistance. University of Agricultural Sciences, Hebbal Campus, Bangalore, Karnataka state, India.

Line	Parents	F ₃ lines (no.)	Plants within each F ₃ line (no.)	Total plants (%)	Incidence (%)
C1	Jaya/W1263	67	80	5360	11.4
C2	W1263/W12787	7	66	462	3.7
C3	Sona/W1263	10	84	840	16.6
C4	Vijaya/W12787	15	84	1260	41.8
Total		99	—	7922	18.4

Table 2. The number of F₃ progeny from crosses for gall midge resistance. University of Agricultural Sciences, Hebbal campus, Bangalore, Karnataka state, India.

Incidence (%)	Classification	Frequency of F ₃ progeny (no.)				Total (no.)	Frequency (%)
		C1	C2	C3	C4		
0– 1	R	—	—	—	—	—	—
1– 5	MR	12	5	0	0	17	17.2
6–25	HR	46	2	9	3	60	60.6
26–50	S	9	0	1	10	20	20.2
> 50	vs	—	—	—	2	2	2.0
F ₃ total no.		67	7	10	15	99	100.0

This study indicates that derivatives of the cross Vijaya/W12787 are highly susceptible to false smut, while those from W1263/W12787 exhibit a degree of resistance. The other two crosses, Jaya/W1263 and Sona/W1263, have intermediate resistance to false smut.

Yield losses due to sheath blight of rice

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We studied yield losses due to sheath blight on the moderately resistant variety IR26 and the highly susceptible line IR1487-372-1-1 at three levels of disease intensity (10, 20, and 50% hills inoculated) at 0 and 100 kg N/ha during the 1975 dry and wet planting seasons at IRRI.

In IR26, the percent yield reduction per unit of disease rating was 2.7 in the plots with 0 N and 2.3 in the plots with 100 kg N/ha. But yield reductions were significant only at the highest level of disease incidence in the plots with higher nitrogen during the dry-season trial. Reductions were insignificant at both N-levels in the wet season. In IR1487 the percent yield reduction per unit of disease rating was 4.4 in the 0 N plots and 4.3 in the 100 kg N/ha

Sheath blight reduced yields significantly on the susceptible line IR1487-372-1-1 at all levels of disease intensity and nitrogen fertilizer; yields were significantly reduced on the moderately resistant variety IR26 only at the highest levels of disease intensity and nitrogen. IRRI, 1975.

Hills inoculated (%)	Yield losses (%) at		Yield ^a (t/ha) at	
	0 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha	0 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha
<i>IR1487-372-1 (susceptible)</i>				
0	—	—	5.7 a	5.8 a
10	7.5	8.6	5.2 b	5.3 b
20	12.2	13.8	5.0 b	5.0 c
50	22.7	23.7	4.4 c	4.4 d
<i>IR26 (moderately resistant)</i>				
0	—	—	6.1 a	7.8 a
10	0.4	2.5	6.2 a	7.6 a
20	6.5	5.1	5.7 a	7.4 a
50	8.8	13.2	5.6 a	6.8 b

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not statistically different at the 5% level.

plots. The levels of disease incidence at both nitrogen levels were statistically significant. The highest percentage of yield loss was about 13 percent for IR26 and 23 percent for IR1487 (see table).

Correlations between disease rating

and yield losses showed that the susceptible variety was very sensitive to the disease—yields decreased rapidly as disease incidence increased in both the 0 and 100 kg N/ha plots. The moderately resistant variety was less affected by the disease (see figure).

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistances

Resistance in some rice strains to first-instar larvae of *Tryporyza incertulas* (Walker) in relation to plant nutrients and anatomical structure of the plants

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The degree of resistance to first-instar larvae of the rice stem borer and the interaction of resistance with certain important plant cell ingredients were studied during 1972–73 in seven rice strains that differ in resistance. To study the possible effects of silica application in inducing stem borer resistance in the rice plant, potassium silicate at 5 g/pot was applied 1) at the time of sowing; 2) during transplanting; and 3) at 7 days after transplanting. The possible effects

on ease of penetration for the larvae and on their survival were also studied. The studies were confined to the first-instar larvae of the rice stem borer on seedlings of Eshwarakora, TN1, W1263, TKM-6, IR20, HR59, and B5580.

There was no uniformity in site of penetration into the plant, larval survival after penetration, or larval ability to cause dead hearts. The uptake of added silica varied among different rices; the variation affected larval survival and growth. The higher silica uptake in IR20 and HR59 led to the wearing and defacing of the insects' mandibles and interfered with the boring and feeding capacity of the larvae. Higher silica content was related to higher insect mortality in IR20, Eshwarakora, and TKM-6; silica content was negatively

IR1487-372-1-1 shows rapidly decreasing yield with increasing intensity of sheath blight disease. Yields of IR26 demonstrate less sensitivity to the disease.